

HOME > KNOWLEDGE BASE > 1. ALFRED RUSSEL WALLACE (1823-1913)

Personal diaries of Mary Elizabeth Podger Wallace (1831-1913)

Three personal diaries of Mary Elizabeth Podger Wallace (née Webster), previously transcribed by the staff at the Natural History Museum, London, have been checked and re-formatted for this blog. With permission from the [Wallace Literary Estate](#), I have combined all Mary's diaries and her household expenses of 1858. This transcription is based on the type-written copies of the original MSS, which are probably kept by the California Historical Society. The diaries were written between 1853-1855, bracketing the years when Wallace had just returned to England from the Amazon (October 1852) and when he left for the Malay Archipelago (February 1854). The diaries chronicled Mary's daily activities — her visits to and from friends and relatives, excursions, her music and German lessons, births, marriages and deaths of the people in her circle. She was a governess or au pair.

Besides mentions of Wallace, the most important event recorded in the diaries would be the visit from John Wallace (1818-1895) in December 1854. After a very brief courtship, John and Mary married on 18 January 1855. John brought his new bride to California, USA and they lived there for the rest of their lives. They had six children: John Herbert, "Bertie", 1856-1934; William George, 1857-1922; Percival Russell, "Percy", 1866-1917; Mary Frances, "May", 1861-1934; Alfred Alexander, 1864-1941 and Arthur Henry, 1868-1947.

Wallace was of course away in the jungles in the Malay Archipelago. By the time the news of the marriage reached him and he was able to reply, it was April 1855.

"This is most sincerely to wish you joy of your marriage, and may you long live in unalloyed domestic happiness. I am sure Mary will make the best of wives: her good temper, good sense, cherf cheerfulness, and industry, are the very qualities to make all go smoo smooth in her new home. I only wish, when my turn comes, as

(The town named Wallace , Calaveras County, 1911. [Courtesy Calaveras Co. Historical Society](#))

St. Anne's Church, Columbia, Tuolumne County, CA. ([Library of Congress](#))

Note on the texts: As the transcripts were made from the type-written copies, it cannot be ascertained whether some misspellings were Mary's or the typist's. In view of this, I have taken the liberty

to provide only the correct spellings. The gaps in some sentences could be due to Mary aborting a thought or they could be due to the typist's inability to read the word/words.

The key people connected to Wallace that were mentioned in the diaries are given below.

1. Wallace (née Webster), Mary Elizabeth Podger, 1831-1913. Married John Wallace, ARW's brother, in 1855. (*Other sources has her birthdate as 1832 or 1834. In the diary of 1854, she said she turned 23.*)
2. Wallace, John. 1818-1895. ARW's brother.
3. Wallace (née Greenell), Mary Ann. 1792–1868. ARW's, Frances and John's mother.
4. Wallace, Alfred Russel, 1823-1913. British naturalist, scientist, explorer, author, social campaigner and humanitarian.
4. Sims, Thomas. 1826-1910. ARW's brother-in-law. Professional photographer who had a succession of studios in Weston-super-Mare, Swansea, London and Tunbridge Wells.
5. Sims, née Wallace, Frances ("Fanny"). 1812-1893. ARW's sister. Married Thomas Sims on 15 February 1849. They did not have any children.
6. Silk, George Charles. 1822–1910. ARW childhood and lifelong friend. Private secretary. Clerk at the London Diocesan Church Building Society and Metropolis Churches' Fund, and assistant to its secretary John Sinclair, archdeacon of Middlesex and vicar of Kensington. (*DGP*)

Diary of Mary Elizabeth Podger Webster. 1853. (WCP[5565](#))

[[1]]

January 1. Spent the first day of the New Year at Greenford. Johnny came to dinner. I returned home in the evening. Aunt much better. Called on Mrs. Martin in the evening.

Jan. 3. Went to Mrs. Harrison's 1st time since holidays. Went with Mrs. Martin to the Society of Arts to see Mr. Sims pictures. Mr. and Mrs. Pringle called.

Tues. Went to Miss Cotton's with Mr. and Mrs. Martin. Did not go to the Harrisons or Wingates. Mother went to Greenford.

Wed. Went to Mrs. Wingate's in the morning. The children were out, had no lessons, staid to dinner, went home, and returned to go with her to Willis' rooms.

Thurs. Mother came home.

Fri. Had first German lesson with Miss Rose. Went to singing.

Mon. Had another German lesson.

Tues. Did not go to Mrs. Wingate's till the afternoon. The little Martin's went with me to a party there. They all enjoyed themselves very much. Rode there and walked home. Poor Willie was very tired.

Wed. Was surprised to find dear Aunt at home when I arrived in the evening. Had a letter from dear George. 12th. Had another German lesson, my third.

Thurs. Mr. Burrows was married. Mrs. Harrison paid me.

Fri. Aunt went home. Had an invitation from <Date?> which I declined.

[[2]]

Mon. Gave up Mrs. Harrison's dancing. Mrs. Wingate called in the morning to say I need not go there. Went in the afternoon to see Mrs. Whiffin and Mrs. Raggatt. Got home to tea. Went in the evening to Mrs. Martin's .

Tues. Took a German lesson without Miss Rose.

Wed. Sent a paper to George.

Thurs. Went from Mrs. W's to Kensington, had a game of cards. Emma gave me a Ticket for the theatre.

Fri. Did not go to Wingate's, had a letter from Miss Woodford respecting her sisters invitation. Had my 5th German lesson.

Sat. Went to Greenford with Uncle.

Sun. Spent at Greenford. Went to church with Aunt. Mr. and Mrs. Guernsey came in the afternoon.

Mon. Went to Chelsea to tea. had a game at chess with Robert.

Tues. Went to the theatre with Mr. Date and friends. Was very much entertained.

Wed. Went to Mrs. Wingate's in the morning. Mrs. H. in the afternoon.

Thurs. Went to meet Mrs. Hovey at Mrs. Martin's. Had a practice. Went into Sims for an hour. Took the ground rent to W. and F. for Father.

Fri. When I went to Wingate's they were out, called on Mrs. _____ and had a German lesson, and paid her.

Sat. Did not go to Piccadilly. Began a letter to George.

Monday. Mother and I called on the Pringles.

[[3]]

Tues. Feb. 1. Spent a delightful evening at Mrs. Martin's . played at cards, got home at 2 o'clock. A very foggy day.

Wed. Went in the evening to Mrs. Hoveys with Mrs. Martin. She has a very nice house. I like the children very much. Wrote to Mrs. Martin.

Thurs. Had a German lesson, and went to Sims to give them a ticket for the concert.

Fri. Went to the concert to sing. Mrs. Hovey fetched me. Mother went also. Mrs. Barron called.

Sat. Took some bracelets from Mrs. Wingate for Miss Rose to look at

Sunday. Mrs. Wallace called in and took tea.

Mon. Wrote to Emma, Mary Ann, and finished George's letter.

Tues. Mr. Hughes called and offered to take a parcel to Australia for us, had a letter from ~~poor~~ Mrs. Lovewell inviting me to go there to a dance on the 7th. Made up my mind to decline as it would be very expensive. Had a German lesson, went to the singing.

Wed. Went to Spitalfield to fetch my drawing away. When I got there he could not find it. Mrs. Ellenby called. Wrote a note to Miss Lovewell declining her invitation.

Thurs. Had a German lesson.

Fri. The children had no lessons.

Sat. Had a holiday went to Mrs. Martin's in the evening.

Sun. Was very poorly, had a mustard plaster on.

Mon. Did not go out all day, very , had a note from Mrs. Lovewell which I was obliged to accept. Fords left.

Tues. Went to Mrs. Wingate. Miss Smith came.

[[4]]

Wed. Feb. 15. Went to Mrs. Harrison's, called at Mrs. Martin's . Kept the house every day after, unable to go out on account of my cold.

Monday. Went to Mrs. Harrison's, was too ill to go to Lovewell's party wrote to that effect.

Tuesday. Called to see Alfred Wallace who was very ill.

Thurs. Had a German lesson. Poor Mr. Moore died.

Fri. Aunt came to town and went out to buy her floor cloth &c, for her house, and I was so disappointed, I was obliged to go out and never saw her.

Sat. Did not go to Mrs. Harrison's in the morning it was so wet. Cleared up in the afternoon and I went out.

Sun. Went to Mrs. Martin's to tea.

Mon. Had a German lesson.

Tues. 1 March. Very snowy, I went to Harrison's not to Wingate. Went to singing.

Wed. Called at Mrs. Roe's to return her Music and staid to tea. Called on Mrs. Sims and stayed an hour.

Thurs. Mrs. Wallace came in the evening and brought us a paper from John.

Friday. A very fine day. Went to Kensington to hear Alfred Wallace lecture. Fred and Emma and Miss Dance went with me. It turned out wet and we were disappointed, but Miss Smith gave me a *[sentence incomplete]*

Sun. Miss Govier called. We had not seen her for years.

Mon. Bought some new satinet to make a new bodice to my dress, *[[5]]* and took it to Mrs. Cooke.

Tues. Began my Music lessons with Mr. Roe for one quarter.

Wed. Wrote to Mary Ann. Had a German lesson.

Thurs. Called on Mrs. Martin, met Miss Smyth at Regent Circus and went to Edgeware Road but were disappointed on our errand.

Fri. 11 Gave Mrs. Wingate notice. Had a German lesson.

Sat. Went to Mrs. Woodford's to tea from there on to Kensington, staid all night with Emma. Had a letter from Mary Ann.

Sun. Spent at Kensington. Went to the Chapel in the morning. Took a walk in the Gardens after dinner. Fred came to tea. we went to Kensington Church.

Tues. Did not take a Music lesson. Mr. Roe was engaged.

Wed. Went to Hyde Park Corner to meet Emma and Miss Dance. Did not see them. walked all the way home. Fred came to tea.

Thurs. Went to a Concert at T. and S. Rooms with Mr. Sims.

Fri. Had a German lesson and a Music lesson.

Sun. Mrs. Smith sent to invite me there to tea to meet Mrs. Davis who I had not seen for some time.

Mon. It was so foggy I did not go to Harrison's. Went to tea at Mrs. Rosy's.

Tues. Took Music lesson, went to singing. W. did not go to Mr. Yates went to Mrs. Martin's in the evening.

Thurs. Miss Rose came Good Friday. Went to church and to Mrs. Martin's in the evening

[[6]]

Mar. 25. Good Friday. Went to Church and to Mrs. Martin's in the evening.

Sat. Went shopping with Mother.

Easter Sunday. Very happy day. Made one or two resolutions which I hope I shall keep.

Tues. Called on Mrs. Roe to make some arrangements for some singing lessons.

Wed. Went to Mrs. Sims to tea. Met Mr. Silk.

Thurs. Had a German lesson. Paid 2/6 on account.

Fri. April 1. Went to Mrs. Roe's to take a music lesson. Miss Rose went to the singing with me.

Sat. Did not go to Mrs. Wingate's. Went to Greenford with Uncle in the Chaise.

Sunday. I intended going home, but was prevented by the wet weather

Monday. Uncle drove me to the train. Got home in very good time. The Burtons came to tea.

Wed. Had a German lesson.

Thurs. Miss Rose called the first time since she left.

Fri. Mr. Roe could not attend the Society. Met with an accident. Mrs. Wallace asked me to stay longer.

Sat. Took tea with Mr. Ditt. Had a German lesson.

Sun. Took tea with Mrs. Sims. in the absence of Mr. Sims.

Mon. I put an advertisement in the Times. Am rather doubtful about getting an answer

[[7]]

Wed. Staid to Mrs. W's. to tea.

Thurs. April 14. My advertisement came out. Our concert came off very well. Fred and Emma went.

Friday. Rather an important day. Had five answers, 1 of which I took notice of. Had a music lesson.

Sat. Took leave of Mrs. Wingate, and received a final answer from Mrs. Greely to my terms.

Mon. Went to Mrs. P's for first time. Every thing appears very straight forward and I hope I shall get satisfaction. Mrs. Sims went with me to buy my first watch.

Tues. A most unlucky thing occurred. I broke my watch, and was obliged to take it where I bought it to get it repaired. Shall not have it for a week.

Wed. The Pringles called.

Thurs. Mother very poorly.

Fri. A little better. went to singing. Had a music lesson.

Sat. Went and fetched my watch home.

Sun. Called to see Miss Rose.

Mon. Went into the square with my children.

Tues. Went to the lecture in the school room.

Wed. Took a book to Mrs. Wingate that I promised to lend her. Found her very cool. Mary Ann called.

[[8]]

May 7th. Had a singing lesson. Went to see Mary Ann and met Fred.

Tues. Had a strange dream about George.

May 8th. Had 3 ~~sing~~ German lessons.

Wed. To the Foundling with Fred and admired the Singing very much. Mary Ann came to dinner and Emma soon after. Miss Govier called.

Fri. I sang a solo at the Harmonic Society.

Sat. I took a singing lesson. Called to see Miss Rose.

Tues. Went to Kensington after tea to see Mary Ann. Mother bought a looking glass for her.

Fri. Took the children to the British Museum, and was very much pleased. Hannah Pringle went with me to have a German lesson, my third.

Mon. Went to tea with Miss Rose. Took Lucy to the Soho Bazaar. Mother very poorly.

Tues. Went to hear French's lecture on Etymology.

Wed. Went to see MacBeth. Alfred Wallace went with me. Met Aunt there.

Fri. and Sat. Very poorly.

Sun. Mary Ann, Emma and Fred came to dinner.

Mon. Wrote to Miss Woodford.

June 1st. Wed. Mary Ann, Emma, and Mr. Tucker came to tea, the first time we saw Mary Ann's intended. They went to the theatre in the evening.

[[9]]

Thurs. June 2. Went to Madame Ditt, my 4th lesson.

Sat. Hannah Pringle called. Mary Ann and Emma afterwards.

Sun. Went to Kensington to be ready in the morning.

Monday. Mary Ann's wedding day. The sun shone brightly. Left the Palace at 9 in the morning, and after the ceremony which took place at St. Margaret's, Westminster, we went to Greenford, arrived at 1/2 past 12 spent a delightful day. The Bride and Bridegroom went off to West Drayton at 8, and Mother and I returned with Mr. Date and Emma in the carriage. Got home at eleven o'clock.

Fri. Went to Sims to a party.

Sat. Had a half holiday.

Thurs. 16. Mr. Hemmings sent me two tickets for Exeter Hall. Went with Mrs. Sims, enjoyed the music and singing very much.

Fri. Poor little Jessie Harrison seized for death whilst I was there, wrote a note to her sister and staid till Mrs. Harrison arrived. Had no music lesson.

Sat. The dear child still living. All the family in great trouble. Saw Mr. and Mrs. Edmund, called at Mrs. Wingate's. They were all out.

Saw Mr. and Mrs. Edmund Harrison.

Tues. Had a letter from Emma.

Fri. Mrs. Punch told me that Holydays would commence on Monday.

Sat. Poor little Jessie buried. Aunt Sally arrived, took us quite by surprise. The Wingates came to tea.

Sun. Very wet and cold. could not take Aunt out.

[[10]]

Mon. June 27. Went to Kensington in the afternoon.

Tues. Expected the Children to come to tea, rather dull weather, did not come. Will and Sally called. Had a letter from Bristol.

Wed. They came and enjoyed themselves very much. Took them to the Zoological Gardens.

Thurs. Aunt Sally, Mother and Mrs. Wallace went to the gardens.

Fri. They went to Kensington.

Sat. Aunt went.

July 2nd. Had a letter from George.

Sun. Father and I went to St. Marks Ch.

Mon. Went to Chelsea to see Miss Woodford. She was not at home.

Thurs. Went to Kensington. Spent a long afternoon. Emma walked with me as far as Piccadilly.

Fri. Made some cuffs for Mrs. Rose.

Sat. Went to Greenford by the 4 o'clock train. caught in the rain before I reached there.

Sun. Went to Church with Aunt.

Mon. Returned home by the first train. Mrs. Harrison was waiting for me to go out with her. Lost my purse with 1/8 in it.

Tues. Went to see Miss Woodford at the Bor's, enjoyed the ride there very much in the boat.

Wed. Expected Emma to tea. Altered my dress a little. The Harrisons went away for a month.

[[11]]

13th. Went for a walk with Mother.

Thurs. Called and took tea with Mrs. Rose.

Fri. Went to Kensington and prepared to start to Somerset with *[incomplete?]*

Sun. Went to Church in the morning with Mr. Rich. in the afternoon went to Stowey Church with Aunt. Called at Clutsom's in the evening.

Mon. Mary Ann came over to spend the day. Mr. Tucker fetched her in the evening.

Tues. Went to the Hills with Aunt and Mrs. Clutsom, enjoyed the scenery much.

Wed. Went to Fairfield, took dinner, went on to Trafford, came on very wet. Unable to return.

Thurs. Nat drove us into Stowey in the afternoon.

Fri. Went to Mrs. Clutsom's to tea.

Sat. Took a very pleasant walk over Castle Hill mound round over Stowey.

Sun. Went to tea at Miss Clutsom. Took a very pleasant walk in the evening with Miss Clutsom, and Mr. F. C. and his wife.

Mon. Intended going to St. Andrews with Postman. Was too late and walked over with Aunt. She returned in the evening. Went out to tea with Mary Ann.

Tues. Miss Tucker came down to tea. Went in the garden and ate plenty of fruit. In the eve. went on the beach gathering

Wed. Had a letter from Father. Walked on the hills after tea.

[[12]]

Thurs. July 28. Went to tea with Miss Tucker. Saw the Church, played on the organ, spent a very pleasant evening.

Fri. Rather stormy. Took a walk to Mr. Rich.

Sat. Walked on the beach by myself in the morning. Went to tea at the house with Mary Ann.

Sun. Went to ~~the~~ St. Andrews Church. Started to go to Sandford in the afternoon, but was prevented by a shower. Had a few friends to tea.

Mon. Went back to Stowey by the Coach. Miss Clutsom came to tea.

Tues. Went to Bristol. Walked on the Downs in the evening.

Wed. Went for a drive to He iery and to the Hill to tea.

Thurs. Mrs. Weston and I went to the Barton's to tea.

Fri. Mrs. Weston busy moving, went to the Hill directly after breakfast, slept there. Mrs. Beyor to tea.

Sat. Mrs. Weston and I started for London. Joseph got us first class tickets, got home comfortably.

Sun. Emma and Fred came took Mrs. W. away to see the Palace.

Mon. Went to Mrs. Harrison's for the first time after the Holidays, called on Mrs. Martin and on the Pringles.

Tues. Spoke to Mrs. H. about leaving. Was rather amused that she would have thought of giving me notice, at the same time took H. Pringle and introduced, thinking she might engage her. Miss Granger called.

Wed. The day Mrs. Weston promised to return. Went and fetched her.

[[13]]

Thurs. Aug 11. Took her to Westminster Abbey. Miss Reynolds and Mr. Black came to tea.

Fri. Went to the Langhorn Bazaar and Pantheon Miss Beeston's and Wm. came to tea.

Sat. Uncle called. Father and Mrs. W. went to Zoological Gardens.

Sun. Went to Chapel in T. C. Rd. Mr. and Mrs. Sims came in even.

Mon. Miss Rose called, Went to spend the evening with her. Emma came to say Good bye.

Wed. Mrs. Turner came to tea.

Thurs. Aunt came to town. We all went to Highgate Cemetery. Mother and Aunt went to Sims.

Fri. Went to the Colossians in the evening with Aunt. Had a letter from Emma.

Sat. All went to Greenford. I drove them from Ealing quite safely although they were rather afraid to trust me.

Mon. Had an adventure. drove to the train, had a good run and got there just in time to see the train move slowly on, but they would not let her get in, quite knocked up. Aunt and Mrs. Weston with me.

Tues. Miss Rose called.

Thurs. Had a few lines from J. D. W. Called on Mrs. Martin, fancied her rather strange. don't think I shall go again for some time.

Fri. Mrs. Roe brought a friend to tea.

[[14]]

Sat. Aug 27. Parted with Mrs. Harrison all very good friends. Started to Greenford again. Saw Fred at the station.

Sun. Went to Church. Mr. and Mrs. Guernsey came over to tea.

Mon. Mrs. Weston came down in the evening went to Mrs. Clark's for a walk. Little Jimmy spent the day with us. Mr. Weston returned to London. Took a walk in the morning. Mrs. Walker came down with Uncle.

Wed. Drove to Harrow. Went over the Church. Saw a door 500 years old, font 700 years, statues of Crusaders and others living in Elizabeth's reign, the ancient church 2000 years old. Came home found a letter from Mrs. P.

Thurs. Sept. 1. Renewed. lessons in Russel Sq.

Fri. Mrs. Weston returned to town.

Saturday. To Bristol I went to Chelsea.

Sun. Went to St. Paul's Chapel, Chelsea, heard a very good sermon, took a walk after and came home after tea in time for Ch.

Mon. Went to Mrs. Martin's . Mrs. Wallace at our house when I returned.

Wed. Hannah Pringle came and begged me to go with her and seek some one to teach us the Globes. Explored all the neighbourhood and were unsuccessful.

Thurs. Called on Mrs. Martin.

Fri. Went to the singing, began the Oratorio of Judas Maccabeans

[[15]]

Sat. Had a letter from Greenford, snowing poor Aunt was ill. Mother resolved to go down next day.

Sun. In the morning to St. James Ch. with Father. Fred came after tea we went to Mary Madger.

Mon. Gave the Children a lesson from Ollendorf's F. Grammar. Took my Music lesson of Mr. Roe the first time since I went out of town.

Tues. Obligated to disappoint Mrs. Martin respecting the Botanical Gardens.

Thurs. Went to the Botanical Gardens.

Sun. Aunt too poorly to go to Church. Went alone. Mr. Podger came down. I returned with him.

Mon. Hannah wanted me to join her in taking lessons on the Globes, but I cannot afford 2/6 a lesson.

Tues. Mother went to Greenford. I had a lesson from Mr. Ditt.

Thurs. Went to Mrs. Martin's . had a game at Chess.

Sat. Went with Mrs. Wallace to see the Earthmen, funny little things very intelligent and amusing.

Mon. Father, Mother and I went to Sims to tea and supper.

Wed. Went to Mr. Ditt and called upon Miss Rose who has changed her lodgings from Stamford Hill to Mr. Crescent.

Thurs. Went to theatre Lilliputians with Mr. and Mrs. Wallace. was very much amused with them, but think them quite Idiots.

Fri. Went to the singing. Met Mrs. Harrison.

[[16]]

Sat. Oct. 1. Took tea at Mrs. Wingate's. The children were all pleased to see them.

Sun. Went to St. James Chapel and as they did not put me into a seat, and I was just sitting in a draught, I walked out again and came home. Mother and I went to Mr. Streabetts in the evening.

Mon. Called on Miss Rose after leaving Mr. Roe.

Thurs. Went to Mrs. Martin's .

Fri. Mr. Sims called. Went to the singing.

Sat. Had a holiday. stayed at home all day and arranged a few things. Wrote letters &c. The day passed with as little ennui as possible but I don't care much for being home all day.

Sun. Father went out all day. Mother and I very cozy, the Ch. opened for the first time since the repairs. Fred came in the afternoon and went to Ch. with me in the evening.

Mon. Went with the Martin's to see the Panorama of Ireland, description by Mrs. Gibbs with songs. Don't think much of it.

Wed. Mrs. Punch went out with the children and myself.

Thurs. Missionary meeting at the school. Bishop of Cape Town attended.

Fri. Went with the Children to the Langham Bazaar staying as usual.

Sat. Chapmans settled their bill making us pay 30/.

Sun. A collection in church for the repairs. Miss Govier came and Mr. and Mrs. Sims had a little of Mozart's Mass went to Ch. in [[17]] the evening.

Mon. Had such a bad cold I did not go down to dinner with the Children as I felt so miserably ill.

Tues. Cold still very bad. Went in the Square. Mr. and Mrs. Sims came in the evening to have a little Music.

Wed. Mrs. P. said I was silly not to stay at home and nurse my cold, so I mean to do so.

Thurs. Staid at home all day. Finished 2 vol. of Queens of England.

Sat. Mrs. P. announced that she could not pay till Nov. much to my disappointment. Went into Sims in the evening. Alfred's book came out the [*Palm Trees of the Amazon and Their Uses*] a very nice work.

Sun. Started for Greenford with every prospect of a wet day but fortunately turned out very pleasant. Uncle poorly Togress came down. I returned same evening and found Mrs. Ellenby at home, who we had not seen for a long time. She staid all night.

Tues. Went to Rose's to tea. Spent a nice evening. Had not seen Miss Rose since her return from France.

Thurs. Went out for a walk with the Children and had a drenching, walked home and went in and bought some colochers.

Fri. Mrs. Cassenble came and fetched from singing to try my dress on.

Sat. Went to Kensington from Russel Sq. ~~Had a long time to wait for a bus. Went with Emma to see if Mrs. Warrington would go with us. A concert in the Assembly rooms. Had a little time to~~ *[text following did not get scanned]*

[[18]]

Mon. Oct. 31. Mr. and Mrs. Sims came in the evening to have a little music.

Tues. Nov. 1. Went to Kensington from Russel Sq. Had a long time to wait for a bus. Went with Emma to see if Mrs. Warrington would go with us. A concert in the Assembly rooms. Had a little time to spare, and tore off to call on Miss Chefgiler. She was out Concert only middling.

Thurs. Mrs. Punch paid me. Went to Mary Land for some boots.

Fri. Took tea at Mrs. Martin's . Bert, Mrs. Hartley and he went to the Harmonic Society with us.

Sat. Uncle called after being to Makley's with Mrs. Rand.

Mon. Paid Mr. Roe. Went to Miss Roe's. staid to Supper.

Wed. Alice's birthday. Had a holiday. went to Piccadilly to buy her a small book on my return. Called at Dr. Shaws and he persuaded me to have a tooth out, which quite upset my plans for the rest of the day. I was very ill in the evening.

Fri. Staid away from the singing.

Sat. Went to call on Mrs. Harrison in the afternoon. At Dell in the evening.

Mon. Mrs. Punch arranged for Sary to stay with her all the morning which I am glad of. Miss Rose called in the evening.

Fri. Called to see if Miss Rose would go to the singing with me she had a bad cold and did not go.

[[19]]

Sat. Nov. 19. Mrs. Punch told me in future the children were to have a whole holiday on Saturday. Uncle came. Emma called in the afternoon, and I went with her to buy something for Fred. Mrs. Breestone called in the evening, and wanted me to go to a Friends of hers to sing.

Tues. Very foggy.

Wed. Fog so bad that we could not see a yard before us. Ann left, could get no conveyance owing to the fog. Had a note from Mrs. Weston.

Thurs. Without a servant. Aunt came to town and remained all night. with us. We were very busy.

Fri. Aunt went home. went to the singing the "Rehearsal" Miss Maddons went with me.

Sat. Did not go to Russel Square, but really had to work very hard as I was Maid of all work, but I hope we shall soon get some one.

Advent Sunday. Staid from Ch. in the morning.

Tues. The Concert was held, very good attendance and went off with great "Eclet".

Wed. Mrs. Martin called in the evening.

Thurs. Dec. 1. Went to hear the Hungarian Band at the Marionable Theatre with Mr. and Mrs. Sims and Mr. Wallace [ARW]. Was much pleased with the performance.

Fri. Went to the lecture, then to the Harmonic Society

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Sat. Dec. 3. Called on Mrs. Wingate, went with her to the City. Dined with her and returned in the evening. Aunt sent us a girl from Greenford who is likely to suit us.

Mon. Mrs. Punch told me she thought of sending the children to school and therefore my services would not be wanted. I was very sorry and herself also. It was what I expected as Alice is so ill.

Tues. Sent the girls some music, played it over to them.

Sat. Went to Russel Square to keep the children in order in Mrs. P's absence. Had fun with them. Called at Miss Rose's in the evening. Miss Wells was there. I liked her very much. recommended a friend of hers to Mrs. Migar.

Thurs. Called on Doctor Fischel to make arrangements for some German lessons. Agreed for 12 for 3 £ take the first one Saturday.

Sat. Went to Dr. Fischel like his place very much. Emma's birthday. Went to Kensington staid rather late.

Tues. Holidays began for a week.

Thurs. Had a German lesson.

Fri. Emma came to tea. gave me a dress for a birthday present went to singing.

Sat. Uncle came to fetch me to go to Greenford. Had a nice ride down, brought home my dress.

Sun. 25. Went to Church in the morning. took a walk in the afternoon with Johnny. Called on Miss Dixon with Aunt. She was very ill indeed. Emma Mr. and Mrs. Gurney the Podgers and a *[sentence incomplete]* [[21]] Mr. Date came to dinner. spent a very pleasant day, had plenty of fun

Tues. Went for a walk in the morning, came home by the 1/2 past 3 train, walked to Regent Street and back to get something I wanted. Went to Sims in the evening to a dance. Enjoyed myself much.

Wed. Quite knocked up with my gaieties.

Thurs. Too unwell to go to Russell Sq; obliged to have a German lesson by appointment.

Fri. Poorly. Began a letter to dear George.

Diary of Mary Elizabeth Podger Webster. 1854. (WCP5566)

[[1]] JANUARY.

Sun. Jan 1. Spent the day at Kensington. Mr. Best very poorly from cold. Fred came in afternoon. went to K. Ch. in the evening. Had a job to get home it was so wet.

Monday. Went to Russell Sq. to Mr. Roe's and called on Mrs. Martin, Mrs. Punch told me not to come while I was so poorly and the weather so cold.

Tuesday. 3. Went to Astley's with Mr. and Mrs. Sims and Mr. ~~and Mrs.~~ W. snowed very much when we came home in the morning. Snow 3 feet deep.

Wed. Went to Albert Smith's with Mr. Sims, Mr. W. and Mr. Silk, very much entertained.

Thurs. 5. Miss Best called. Had a German lesson.

Friday. 6. Had a few friends to tea, went off very well. Sim's party and Fred. Emma unable to come and a few others. The last time Alfred will be with us, I dare say.

Sunday. 8. Father and I went to Sims to dinner. Mother came to tea. Spent a pleasant day. Alfred's birthday.

Monday. 9. Not a very fine day, but we went to the Zoological Gardens, saw the anteater, a very curious creature, feeds here on bugs and milk. Sims went with me.

Wednesday. 11. Annie Smith called with her brother, staid tea.

Thursday. 12. Had a German lesson.

Friday. 13. Went to the Russell Sq. I suppose for the last time professionally. The children go to Greenwich to-morrow. Went [[2]] with Mrs. Punch to the Pantheon. I feel very sorry to be going to leave but hope soon to get somewhere else.

Saturday. Jan. 14. Mrs. Sims asked me to come in the evening, had a quadrille.

Sunday. 15. Expected Mrs. Lewis to dinner but she did not come. The weather no doubt prevented her. Went home with Mrs. Martin in the evening.

Monday. 16. Mr. Roe gave me a ticket for Street, but I was tired and gave it to Mrs. Sims, who went. Went to Spitalfields.

Tuesday. 17. Emma, Fred, Mrs. Pringle came to tea. Mr. and Mrs. Sims at 5, had some music, spent a pleasant evening.

Wednesday. 18. A German lesson at 1/4 to 4.

Thursday. 19. Singing lesson at 3. Paid Ann Astley. Mrs. Martin came to tea. Advertisement came out.

Friday. 20. Had two letters, a miserable day of suspense, answered one at Ealing, the other was to have an interview to-morrow.

Saturday. 21. Went to Maida Vale to see Mrs. Kemp who seems a very nice person, beautiful house, asked 60. She says that is the only thing, money too much, will give 50, don't know what to do.

Sunday. 22. Took a walk to C. T. to find Miss Rose, did not succeed. Anne Smith came staid tea, went to Ch with me in the eve. Called in at Sims, took leave of Alfred I suppose though I did not take formal leave. Which is at all times a painful task.

[[3]]

Monday. Jan 23. Wrote the first thing to Mrs. Kemp offering my services for 55 £ had a letter from Ealing. must go there tomorrow. Took no Music lesson. A. W. (Alfred Wallace) went.

Tues. German lesson at 1/2 past 4. Wrote this at Ealing after having had an interview with Mrs. Fenton who is a nice person, rather blue and sentimental. asked 40 £ for 5 hours, obliged to wait more than an hour at the station where I write this with the wind blowing on all sides. Dare say I shall have a fine cold. No dinner.

Wed. Went to see Mrs. Kemp agreed with her and if all is satisfactory with Mrs. Pain to go on Tuesday. Found Aunt when I returned home.. Went to Kensington in the afternoon to tea. Mrs. Date poorly.

Thurs. Called on Mrs. Punch, she fancies the walk will be too much, met Mrs. Martin at 1/2 past 11. Went to Shoolbred. Called on Miss Rose at Camden Town.

Fri. After Mrs. Kemp had seen Mrs. Punch she called upon me in her Brougham to say that everything was quite satisfactory and she expects to see me on Tuesday. I am dreadfully afraid it will be more than I can manage, but I must do my best. Mrs. Wallace came in the evening. Wrote to Mrs. Wingate to know if she wanted a clerk for Mrs. Wallace's friend.

Sun. Not very well. staid from Ch. in the morning. Poor Mrs. Ellenby came to dinner, staid all night.

Mon. Went to Mr. Roe in the evening. He played some pieces to me and kindly said he should consider it no lesson. Gave we a ticket for Concert. Went with Mrs. Treet. Mary Norton's song and dance of Lovers very entertaining.

[[4]]

Tuesday. 31. German lesson at 8. My first day at Mrs. Kemp's. My pupil is a great girl as big as myself. I dare say I shall be able to get on. she is very backward in all but singing and Music. Went to Mrs. Sims in the evening.

Wed. Feb. 1. Turned out a wet day, but Mrs. Martin and myself went to Exeter Hall to a Concert, Mendelsohn's and Mozart's Music enjoyed it very much.

Fri. 3. A dense fog, almost all day, lost my way and nearly ran against a cow which was on the pathway.

Mon. 6. Go to Mrs. Kemp's every day, got a very dull pupil find it very unsatisfactory. I don't think I shall stay very long for she gives more trouble than any I ever had.

Tues. 7. German lesson.

Fri. 10. Met Mr. Sims and Miss Ellis in the Park and on my way to Carlton Villas.

Sat. 11. Much pleased to see Emma walk in after tea. Mrs. Date was at Windsor and she came to stay the night at our house.

Sun. 12. Went home with her and to Mr. Berkhaus to dinner enjoyed myself very much, remained all night.

Mon. 13. Walked from K. To Mrs. Kemp's got there in very good time end enjoyed the walk very much.

Tues. 14. Mrs. and Miss Bustons came to tea and supper. Played at cards and spent a very pleasant evening.

Wed. 15. Went to Sims to tea to meet the Townsends, Alfred [[5]] Wallace came home in the night. All glad to see him.

Thurs. 16. Had an invite from Miss Woodford. Went about my dress. Mrs. Russell brought Mother a dress. Miss Wilkinson came. We had some Music.

Fri. 17.

Sat. 18. Took my German lesson at 6. went to the Hampstead Rd. and bought some gloves, flowers &c. for the party. Mrs. and Miss Woodford called to say the party was to be on Friday. next instead of Wednesday. as was first settled.

Sun. 19. Mrs. Newis came to dinner the old lady has not been able to come before this Xmas.

Mon. 20. Had my dress tried on that I intend to wearing to Woodford's on Friday.

Tues. 21. Had a note from Emma telling me May Keone was confined on Sunday. with a still born baby, and was very ill.

Thurs. Took Brener's Guide into Alfred Wallace. had a nice walk to Kilburn. Emma Fred and Sydney Clutsom came to tea. Sydney is coming to live in London. Had some music in the evening. Had a letter from Mrs. Weston.

Fri. 24. My long expected visit to Woodford. I did not get home till 1/2 past 5 in the morning did not feel so tired as I feared.. Louise rebelled and we did not take our usual walk which I was not sorry for, being rather too tired

Mon. 27. as it was his wish. I did not en [[6]] joy it at all, dreadfully tired and uncomfortable.

Tues. Feb. 28. Mrs. Kemp paid me for the month. I complained that Louise did not get on so well as I wished. She gave me an invitation for Wednesday week. Poor Mrs. Chapman, the first time we have seen her since the Captain's death.

Mar. 1. Wed. Spent the evening with Mrs. and Miss Wilkinson. They taught me to read my Italian song.

Fri. 3. Emma called, went to the singing. Mrs. Sims sent to ask me to go in there as it was Alfred's last night. I was out and did not go.

Sat. 4. Had a German lesson, each one has greater interest as I understand more.

Sun. 5. Spent the afternoon with Miss Rose took tea. She came back with me and went to Church.

Mon. 6. Mrs. Martin called in the evening to inquire if we could tell her of a servant we recommended Ann to her

Wed. 8. Mr. Kemp went to Court. I declined going to their party, called on Mr. Levy, not home. Made some purchases in Regent St. ~~Went~~ Met Mrs. Martin and Willie.

Thurs. 9. Had a music lesson of Mr. Roe, my last, I suppose it will be. Had a note from Mr. Levy informing me of his terms in answer to my letter.

Fri. 10. German lesson. Miss Rose came to the singing. Went a little way home with her.

Sat. 11. Louise went to see some pictures. I left at 2 o'clock went home and started to Greenford by the 11 o'clock train [*illeg.*] [[7]] the walk across the fields. Read some of the Sketch Book. Uncle was surprised to see me.

Sunday. March 12. Uncle and Aunt wen to Ch. with me, beautiful day. They went to the station with me. Found I was too late for the train, and returned by the Bus.

Mon. 13. Mr. Wilkinson ordered off to Turkey with very short notice. Started this evening at 1/2 past 7. Only heard of it yesterday. I went to Mrs. Sims in the evening.

Tues. 14. When I left Carlton Villas, went to Kensington to stay all night. Mr. Date was in Stowey respecting some horses which he thinks of buying.

~~Wed. 15.~~ Left Kemp's at 4. Went to Kensington. Emma was not at home. She had gone to the Station with Mr. John Weston. I was too late to see him.

Wed. 15. Went to tea with Emma at Mrs. Castles. Fred is lodging there. played at Cribbage. Spent a very nice evening.

Thurs. 16. Left Carlton Villas at 1/2 past 2 and went home very tired indeed. Glad to see dear Mother again.

Fri. 17. Too poorly and tired to go to the singing.

Sat. 18. Called on Miss Morton in the evening.

Sun. 19. In bed nearly all day. Poorly with cold. Did not go to Ch. all day.

Tues. 21. Left Carlton Villas at 1/2 past 2 and went to Mrs. Ragetts to tea. The two boys went home with me to show me what Mr. R. thought would be nearer. [*text missing*] [[8]] is quite a new style. Arranged for 3 guineas the quarter.

Mar. 23. Thurs. Called at Mrs. Ragetts with Louise to enquire whether the boys got home safely. Went to Mr. Fischel in the evening to make appointment for a lesson.

Fri. 24. Took a German lesson and went to the singing afterwards. Concert to take place on the 4th.

Sat. 25. Called in Oxford Street for my umbrella. Walked all around the Edgeware Rd. and bought a piece of Music, just what I wanted , very cheap. Was dreadfully tired. Mrs. Wilkinson came home from London.

Sun. The Bishop of Oxford preached a beautiful sermon. A collection for the repairs of the Ch. Went with Mr. and Mrs. Sims for a long walk to Holloway. Rode home. Went home in the evening with Mrs. Martin.

Tues. 28. Mrs. Chapman went away.

Wed. 29. Left Mrs. Kemps at 3. Called on Mr. Whiffin. He was not at home. Walked to Orchid street. Had to spin out the time not to be there before five.

Thurs. 30. Mr. Kemp went to the Drawing room. Louise went out with them early. I went with Mr. and Mrs. Sims to the Panopticon in Leicester Sq. which is just open. A nice place, something after the same principal as the Blytechure, but on a grander scale.

Fri. 31. The rehearsal, had a note from Miss Woodford telling me of Miss Lovewell's wedding. *[Text following did not get scanned]* [[9]] if they had heard from Mr. H.

Sun. April 2. Expected to see Emma and Fred. Annie Smith and I returned with her to see Mr. Davis. Went to Peach St. Church with her in the even.

Tues. Our Harmonic Concert took place. Fred and Emma , Annie Smith and Mrs. Warrington came and went also They were very much entertained. Walked home with Miss Roe.

Thurs. 6. Spent the evening with Wilkinson's.

Fri. 7. Mother went to Kensington to tea and I went from Carlton Villas and met her. Rode back in time for the singing.

Sat. 8. Confirmation at Christs Ch. Wilkinsons went away to Ireland.

Mon. 10. Mrs. Lewis came , her place was being painted so we did not like to refuse her coming. Poor old lady takes possession of the drawing room.

Tues. 11. Thought to have gone to the Marionette Theatre but it was closed during Passion week. Annie Smith came to tea and went with me to return a book to Madame Ditt.

Wed. 12. Louise went to Sydenham. I left at 11. Went to Madame Ditt, had an hours conversation instead of going to Fischel. Went to Levy. Tried to match some lace.

Fri. 14. Good Friday. After dinner made my first attempt at Wax Flowers. Think if I had time to practice I should soon master it. Miss Rose came to tea.

Sat. 15. Went to Madame Ditt, but I don't consider I had a lesson. She had several friends and I left in 1/2 hour. Miss Rose [[10]] came in the evening and went to church with me. Went partly home with her and called at Mrs. Sims. On my return found he had been at our house thinking I was offended.

Sun. April 16. Easter Sunday. Went to the early service which was not over till 10. Mrs. Sims was with us. Annie went to Greenford. I went in to Mrs. Sims in the evening.

Tues. 16. Ventured to ask Mrs. Kemp for a holiday for to-morrow. I could see she did not much like granting favours so I hope as long as I remain it will be the last time.

Wed. 19. Went to Russell Sq. met with a very kind reception, Staid and took the children to the Pantheon. Returned to dinner with them. Went to Levy at 5 and jumped into a Bus and went to Kensington. found they had a party. Mr. and Mrs. Martin, Mr. Beckham, and Fred. Had a game at Cribbage and got home about 10.

Thurs. 20. Mrs. Ellenby came. Poor old lady, too late for the train. Staid all day. Mother went to Greenford and did not return that night.

Fri. 21. Miss Rose came to the singing. Returned to supper and wrote a note to Miss Maddox. Mother came home from Greenford. Mrs. Ellenby went away.

Sat. 22. Mrs. Grant gave notice.

Sun. 23. Mrs. Sims called and asked me to go after Church. Mrs. Sims Senior was there. Had some music. Brought me a package from Edward.

Mon. 24. Sent a letter to dear George enclosed in one to Mr. Brooks. *[text following did not get scanned]* [[11]] apology, and promised to go on better. Don't know how long it will last.

Wed. April 26. Fast day. Prayers read for the prevention of war. Went to Miss Rose's after tea at Sims' about 1/2 past 9. Staid till nearly 11. Wished Mr. Sims farewell.

Thurs. 27. Levy offered to take me to the Opera or Theatre at any time. Mrs. Grant left.

Sat. 29. Bought a bonnet and several other things in Oxford Street and at Shoolbred. Mrs. Kemp paid me.

Sun. 30. Expected Emma, but it was so wet that she was prevented. Went to Mrs. Martin's in the afternoon.

Mon. May 1. paid Mr. Mard and called on Dr. Fischel to make enquiries about more lessons.

Tues. 2. Mrs. Ca came. Paid her 1£ off.

Wed. 3. Mr. Eaton called, took a music and German lesson. Levy walked to the Circus with me, expected to have met Miss Rose but it turned out wet.

Sun. 7. Went to Kensington, walked all the way. met Fred and Emma. Went to Greenford by the 10 o'clock train. Mr. and Mrs. Brown were there the first time of meeting them. Mary A. Wilson came down after tea, Enjoyed Fred's company very much.

Mon. 8. Went to Mrs. Martin's after tea. Had some practice. She was very glad to see me.

Tue. 9. Mrs. Wallace came in in the evening.

Wed. 10. Great preparation at Kemps for a dinner party. At [[12]] luncheon Mrs. K. asked me if I would come. I declined as the notice was so short. Took my music lesson.

Thurs. 11 May. Called on Miss Rose and met John Baldwin. Went to Annie Smiths. Mr. S. walked home with me. Miss R, will not go to D. L. with Levy.

Fri. 18. Went with Louise to Miss Napents rehearsal. Returned home with her to tea. Left there in time for our own rehearsal.

Sat. 13. Mother came across the Park to meet me. Had a nice walk with her.

Sun. 14. William Sully came in the afternoon. We had not seen him since Christmas.

Mon. 15. Went down to Regent St. after tea to get the Creation. Met Levy. Hannah Pringle called soon after I returned.

Tues. 16. Annie Smith came. Mrs. Sims called to ask me to go to Newman St. with her which I did.

Wed. 17. The Concert came off. Not at all pleased with it. Very well attended. Mr. Roe's "Bonnie Wee Wife" was the best of anything.

Thurs. 18. Went to Levy's. He was at the Concert. Called at Sim's. Went to Miss Killicks in Albert St. Did not enjoy myself at all. Was dreadfully tired and not at all pleased.

Fri. 19. Met Mr. Kemp and Louise at the Royal Academy at 8 o'clock. Was very much pleased with the Paintings. Walked all the way back to Kilburn. Went to the singing, "Creation"

Sun. 21. Rather surprised not to see Mrs. Martin at Church. Miss Govier came in the evening. went to Church with me.

Mon. 22. Called on Mrs. Martin. heard of her trouble. Mr. [[13]] Martin out of the business and quite done up. Poor woman in sad trouble. Mrs. Furse brought her baby.

Tues. May 23. Called on Dr. Fischel to arrange for a lesson. He was much pleased to show me his little daughter for the first time.

Wed. 24. Botanical Fete. Mrs. Kemp brought me to W. Church in the carriage at 2 o'clock. Called on Mrs. Burn on my way to Levy for a few minutes. Levy offered me a ticket for the Philharmonic Society. Hurried home and dressed. Met him there. Very much delighted indeed.

Thurs. 25. Heard more trouble from Mrs. Martin respecting Patrick. Called.

Fri. 26. Met Miss Rose and Friends at the Singing. Mother took Sarah home to Greenford by her wish after staying with us all the winter.

Sat. 27. Had a note from Mr. Date telling me that Mrs. Rich was very ill. Dear Emma obliged to go down immediately. Arrived at Bridgewater at 8 this evening. A conveyance to meet her to convey her to Stoney.

Sun. 28. Mr. Sims came in the afternoon. I went to Mr. Langs Church with them in the evening.

Mon. 29. Intended going to Miss Woodfords but the weather turned out very unfavourable.

Tues. 30. The Roses took possession. I suppose we shall have till September. Had a note from Emma telling us that aunt was better

Wed. 31. Went to Levy. Got on only middling. The creature gives me no encouragement. Finds great deal of fault and says [[14]] I could do more if I liked. Now that is impossible for I practice steadily every day. He gave me some tickets for German Reading.

Thurs. June 1. Had a German lesson and L congratulates me on the progress I have made.

Fri. 2. Miss Rose and I went to the German reading. Levy played the principal part. Martha Stabback sung. Did not understand much of the German Faust.

Sat. 3. Just called on Mrs. Martin. She was out so went down the the road and made a few purchases.

Sun. 4. Expected M. Sully. As usual he disappointed. Went to tea at Mrs. Martin's . Poor woman, she is in great trouble not knowing how things will be settled.

Tuesday. Answered an advertisement for German lessons.

Wed. 7. Mrs. Rose came. Did not go to Kemps. Called on Miss Woodford in the Borough. They are in trouble. John wants to go to sea. Went from there today and then on to Kensington. Met Miss Croker who returned with Emma.

Fri. 9. Went to the Singing. A Collection made for the money Mr. M. took off. Miss Rose came from Paris.

Sat. 10. Took my first German lesson with Mr. Giere.

Mon. 12. Kemps brought me in the carriage to M. Church Flower show at 1/2 past 1. Had fine fun with the Roses. Went to Dr. Fischel and took back some books he lent me. Going to give him up for a short time. Called on Mrs. Chapman. *[Start of sentence did not get scanned]* called and I went to Camden town with *[[15]]* her to look at some apartments, near Jeffrey's Terrace.

Wed. June 14. Levy promised me some tickets for Concerts.

Thurs. 15. Miss Rose went to Witney to meet Mr. Baldwin. persuaded to stay all night.

Sat. 17. Emma came to tea. brought Mrs. Sims and Miss May from Bridgewater. staid to tea. had some music. Mr. Giere came. Had a short lesson. Emma told me Joseph Weston, avait été a Londres et ne pas benoit nous vois.

Wed. 21. Went to the Crystal Palace with the Roses. Admired the Grounds very much, but the Palace seems very empty what little I saw of it.

Thurs. 22. Took my music lesson. Miss Rose and Mrs. McKenzie came to Levy's to hear me. Went on to Kensington. Mrs. River came home before I left.

Fri. 23. Ann came back again. Mrs. Martin left the market. Went to the singing. Bought a bonnet.

Sat. 24. Mrs. Kemp allowed Louise to go to a Morning concert at Besthaven rooms. Levy gave me a ticket to admit 4. Met Miss Cath Rose and Mrs. McKenzie. Enjoyed it very much. Went to Regents St. to order some music. Had some Tea and returned rather late.

Sun. 25. Went to Greenford by the 9 o'clock train. Went to Church with Aunt. Johnny Guernsey was there and has taken up his abode. I hope he will assist Uncle.

Mon. 26. Met Mr. and Mrs. Gales they drove me home. Miss May, Emma, Mr. Date &c. came to tea. Miss Rose gave me 8 tickets to go to Mr. Roe's Concert. Mother and I went. Had a German lesson.

[[16]]

Tue. June 27. Miss Rose went to Paris. Took music with her. Called at Sims in the evening.

Wed. 28. Mrs. Rose had her pocket picked and 5£ stolen. Had a Music lesson. Mr. Baldwin came.

Thurs. 29. Went to Kennedy's to have my hair done. Lost my combs and lace tie. Mrs. Sims and Edward went to Mr. Levy's Concert, Wallis' Romus with me, enjoyed it very much. Heard Will attended. Heard "Gordoni"

Fri. 30. Called to see Mrs. Burton after the singing. She had expected Mother to tea and supper, but she did not go.

Sunday. July 2. Not very well in the morning, did not go to Church. Went in the afternoon to Mrs. Martin's. Went to Mrs. Levy's Church with her, heard that Mrs. Martin was a Roman Catholic.

Mon. 3. Miss Rose went to the Morning Concert. I could not go. Miss Gine called came.

Wed. 5. Levy gave me a ticket for a Concert at Honour Sq. Went with Miss Rose.

Sat. 8. Mrs. Wingate called with Freddy, Wanted to borrow a Macker. I did not see her.

Mon. 10. Paid Miss Giere.

Tues. 11. Left Carlton Villas early end went to see Miss Wingate, with a kind reception.

Wed. 12. Made up my mind not to have any more lessons from Levy but Miss Rose wants me to.

[[16]]

Thurs. 13. Aunt and Mrs. Croker came to tea. Wanted me to go to Kensington with them. Annie Lautt called.

Fri. 14. Intended going to Kensington but it looked so dull I thought it would rain and did not go.

Sun. 16. Mrs. Martin, Mr. Sims and myself went to the Temple Church. Much pleased with it. Walked in the Inn Gardens. Freddy Wingate came to say his Mother wanted to see me. Went in the evening Park after Church with Cath.

Mon. 17. Went to Mrs. Wingate's. She wanted me to go there to teach the Children two or three times a week. I could not do so but spoke for Mis Rose. who is going tomorrow.

Wed. 19. Levy gave a Ticket for a Concert at H. Sq. Rooms. Went with Edward Sims.

Thurs. 20. Miss Giere came.

Fri. 21. Told Mrs. Kemp I was really too unwell to go on if she did not give me a rest for a day or two. She gave me unwillingly till Tuesday.

Sat. 22. Went to Rolandi's in the morning for Tristram, went to the Palace in the afternoon and found they had fled. Walked from there to Paddington. Took first class return ticket for Monday.

Sun. 23. Mr. and Mrs. Hobbs came to dinner. Wanted me to return with them.

Mon. 24. Uncle finished Hay making. Seen the last load come in. Wrote to Emma and Mrs. Weston. Came home by the 9 o'clock train.

Tues. 25. Read Tristan with Miss Giere. Staid at home all day. *[text following did not get scanned]*

[[18]]

Wednesday. July 26. Went back to Kemp's. Louise glad to see me. Went to Levy's.

Sun. 30. Staid from Church in the morning. Father and I went to Mr. Stuarts Church in the evening and for a walk after.

Mon. 31. The Kemps went out for the day. I returned at 11. Called on Mrs. Wingate in the afternoon. Mrs. Sims came in the even.

Aug. 1. Tuesday. Went from Carlton Villas to London bridge to see Miss Woodford. Had an amusing omnibus companion. John came home with me to Charing Cross.

Wed. 2. A good Music lesson. Levy very agreeable. Went with me to the Circus.

Thurs. 5. Was an hour after my time at Kemps. They were very civil and as it was so wet Mrs. Kemp sent me up a glass of Brandy and water.

Fri. 4. Very wet. Miss Rose went to Regents Street with me to buy a dress. got dreadfully wet.

Sat. 5. Made the skirt of my dress.

Sun. 6. Went to Mrs. Martin's after dinner, to Mr. Lacy's Church in the evening. Mrs. Hartley and Garry came home with me.

Mon. 7. Mr. Kemp said he wanted to speak to me, and it was to request I would not leave. Mr. Forbes and Louise together. Very strange of him, I think.

Tues. 8. Mr. and Mrs. Kemp went to Scotland. The McKenzies left also *[text following did not get scanned]* [[19]] see the Velose off. They went to Gravesend and did not return till 8 o'clock P.M. Mrs. Joseph does not intend calling upon us at all, I think he seems to have made up his mind not to do so.

Aug. 20. Sun. Mr. and Mrs. Weston and self went to Greenford. Met Mr. and Mrs. Brown there. Went to Church and Johnny walked to the train with me after tea.

Only just arrived in time.

Mon. 21. Joseph Weston called in the morning to know if there were any letters. I did not see him. Mrs. Scoutleberg came and took tea with us. The first time since she has been married.

Tues. 22. Mrs. Weston came up from Greenford and returned the same night.

Wed. 23. Had a German lesson. Must begin to work again now. I have had so much pleasure lately. Finished Tristram.

Thurs. 24. Aunt and Mrs. Weston at home when I got there after after tea. Mrs. Weston and I went to Regents Street to buy some music &c. Aunt brought Mary Ann Podger to supper.

Fri. 25. Mrs. Wallace and the Sims came in to spend the evening. We were all very merry. Mother went with them to see the Duke of Wellington's car.

Sat. 26. Mrs. Weston and Aunt went home in the morning. All seems to be quiet and we must return again to business after this fortnight's pleasure.

Sun. 27. I was not at all well, did not go out of the house all day. Mrs. Beeston and her daughters came to tea and supper.

Mon. 28. Went to see Mr. Sims who has had an attack of Cholera. He looks quite altered. Annie Smith called there and I went with her.

[[20]]

Tue. 29. Tues. Met Edward Sims in the Park and was bored with his company. Mrs. Forbes never came to give Louise her lesson.

Wed. 30. Mr. Sims overtook me and walked to Carlton Villas with me. Edward came in the evening to show us his first specimens of likenesses taking as visit. Paid Mr. Roe.

Thurs. 31. Went in the evening to call on Mrs. Pringle, on Mrs. Martin. Met Annie Smith and she walked home with me. Edward Sims overtook me and went with me.

Sept. 1. Fri. Mr. and Mrs. Kemp came home quite unexpectedly. Gave me a holiday for the rest of the day. Got home about 11. Prevailed on Mother and Mrs. Wallace to go to the Crystal Palace which they both did and really enjoyed themselves very much. Left about 1/2 past 6. Came in the boat from London Bridge to Hungerford. Walked here.

Sun. 3. Went to Church morning with Cath. Mr. and Mrs. Burn came in the afternoon, staid to tea. Mrs. Burn went to church with me in the evening.

Mon. 4. Told Mrs. Kemp that unless she gave me a holiday I really must leave and gave her notice for this day month, which she is to consider over.

Tues. 5. Mrs. Kemp told me I was to have a fortnight holiday the end of the month and I was not to leave.

Wed. 6. Settled with Miss Giere up to last Wednesday. This begins a new lesson.

Thurs. 7. Met Mr. Sims Senior in the morning. Had a letter [[21]] from Aunt telling me she had to walk from Ealing the Saturday. she went home.

Sept. 8. Fri. Annie Smith called with Josephine who I have not seen since she went to France. She is a very nice girl.

Sat. 9. Had a note from Mrs. Raggett just after returning from Regent St. inviting me there on Monday. Had to go off to buy a pair of cuffs.

Sun. 10. Went to St. Marks Church in the morning with Father for a walk in the park with Mrs. Rose in the afternoon. To church and Sims in the evening.

Mon, 11. Went from Kemps to Mr. Raggett. Met Mrs. J. Walker for the 1st. piece, and Mr. Walker &c. came along with Mr. and Mrs. Burns. Was surprised to find Mr. Weston there when I arrived.

Tues. 12. Mr. Weston walked as far as Zoological Gardens with me. He went in. Returned to Bristol same day. Miss Rose made me a present of a Big oak Broach and bracelets.

Wed. 13. Miss Giere came. Took a German lesson.

Thurs. 14. Met Mr. and Mrs. Raggett as I was walking down the Edgware Road with Louise in the afternoon. Had a good practice in the evening and read some German and English.

Fri. 15. When I got home was-surprised to hear Mr. Date had called. I went to see him after tea. Emma he had left at Bristol. He returned there on Sunday. to stay a day or two. Young Mr. Date walked home with me. Not a very pleasant evening for walking. Rather damp. young Date is a very second rate person; very agreeable but not quite "La Mode"

[[22]]

Sept. 17. Sun. Ought to have gone to Burns but didn't feel inclined. Called to ask how Mrs. Wallace was after her illness. Went to Church with Cath.

Mon. 18. went to Regent Street with Cath to get some Music and met Orpheus Runn. Called to Sims when I returned to inquire how Mrs. Wallace was.

Tues. 19. Aunt wrote to ask me to go to Caversham with her Thursday.

Wed. 20. Went with Miss Rose to Miss Nunns, made arrangements with her and Mr. Orpheus to give me lessons for 7/ per week

Thurs. 21. Took a German lesson. I suppose my last for some time as I must give them up.

Sat. Mr. Kemp wrote me a note requesting that I should take the part of Nerissa in their "Merchant of Venice". Wanted me to return to hear them rehearse it. Went to Mrs. Martin's to have my dress tried on. Had a game of chess. Had a note from Aunt to go there next day.

Sun. 24. Met Mr. Brown at the Marble Arch and rode to Greenford with him. Returned with them to the top of North Audley St. Took a cab home as it was very wet.

Mon. 25. My holiday commenced. Went to Regent St. to pay Addison. Miss Rose's account. Busy preparing for the wedding..

Tues. 26. The party assembled and walked to Church about 1/2 past 9. Mr. Charles Baldwin married them, All very merry. They went off at 2 in the afternoon.

Wed. 27. Helped Mrs. Rose pack Cath's things, hard at work [[23]] all day. Went to take Mrs. Wingate a piece of cake. Sims walked with me and called for me.

Sept. 28. Thurs. Started to Greenford by the 1/2 past 10 o'clock train. Aunt and Johnny met me at Ealing. Mr. Wallace had taken all his family down. Mrs. Merryweather and her daughters called in the afternoon.

Fri. 29. Went to Northott in the afternoon, only John at home. Staid to tea with him and returned early. Then went up to the Manor to see the Smyths They walked home with us.

Sat. 30. In the morning wrote to Mrs. Gurney and asked her to come to tea this evening as the Smiths were coming. She could not do so, but Mr. Smeathman came to tea. Amused us very much with his travels. Told me and Miss S. our phrenology. thinks I shall travel. He is a very estimable man, I think. The girls made very free with him.

October 1. Sunday. Father and Mother came down. All went to the Church. Had a beautiful sermon, and thanksgiving for the abundant harvest. Miss Jones and Stamey came and Mr. Smeathman went a little way home with them. Very foggy.

Mon. 2. Aunt and Johnny rode to Northott. I walked as I promised. Started soon after dinner. Met Miss Jones and Stamey like them both very much and Mr. S. better than ever. The bells rang for the Victory at Sebastopol.

Tues. 3. Called at the with Miss Aunt and had a swing. Aunt and Jack drove me to Ealing. Met the Smiths there. Had to wait a long time for the train. Miss Woodford

called in a and wanted me to go back with her. Was not home in time.

[[24]]

October 4. Wed. Had a letter from Louise. They return on Friday. Walked to Kensington and had tea with Emma and Mr. Date called on Miss . Came with me as far as the Paddington Station. they looked all the better.

Thurs. 5. Walked to Hereford took a Boat and went to London Bridge to see Miss Woodford. She had just gone out. Returned in same way. Was very tired. Called at Sims in the evening. Mrs. Thornton came too.

Fri. 6. Went to Rolandi's in the morning. Called on Mrs. Rose in Fitzroy Sq. in the afternoon. Busy reading "Ten Thousand a year".

Sat. 7. Miss Woodford called in the Chaise and took me home with her to Chelsea. spent a very quiet evening by ourselves with Music and Singing. She played a piece from the Prophet and I liked it very much. She sent it to me on Monday.

Sun. 8. Went to their own Chapel in the morning and in the evening went by boat from Chelsea to Waterloo bridge and went to hear Mr. Cummings preach in Covent Gardens. Liked him very much.

Mon. 9. Went to Kemps again. Emma and Miss Chassille came to tea. Fred and his brother not able to come.

Tues. 10. Took my first lesson of Miss Nunn. Liked her plan very much. Got home very tired. Miss Lewis came.

Wed. 11. Miss Woodford comes to take her first German lesson, expected Miss Giere but she did not come.

Thurs. 12. Mrs. Wallace brought a letter from John saying "he thought he should be home by Christmas". [[WCP356](#)] Mrs. Grant came the [[25]] 1st. time and staid to supper.

October 13. Fri. Had no Singing lesson. Miss Nunn was ill. Had a note from Levy to say he should be happy for me to resume my Music lessons.

Sat. 14. Went to the 1st rehearsal at Kemps. did not like the thought of it but found it was not so unpleasant as I had feared. Got through it very well. Mr. Kemp invited me to go there next Wednesday. Had a letter from Agnes. Mr. Sibley came to York and Albany with ~~them~~ me, then I rode home.

Sun. 15. Went to Sims in the afternoon to read them a letter we had from Mr. Bell about dear George. They went to Church with me and I returned to supper with them.

Mon. 16. Had a singing lesson. Mrs. Martin came in the eve to try on a net body to wear to Kemps with my blue dress.

Tues. 17. Went out to buy some shoes and gloves.

Wed. 18. Mr. Kemp too unwell to appear in the evening. Miss Little did not come nor Mrs. Eidersium, but we spent a very pleasant evening. I danced every dance. Tom took me into supper. Like Mrs. Forbes very much. Mr. Forbes came to supper and played a little.

Thurs. 19. Glad to get home again after being away so long. Had a singing lesson.

Fri. 20. Miss Woodford came to take a German lesson of Miss Giere. She seems to like it very much. It seems so strange to hear another person learn what is now so easy to me.

Sat. 21. Mr. Kemp not at all well. staid home all day. Mr. Forbes came to give his Music lesson and Mr. Kemp had it and re- *[text following did not get scanned]* ^{[[26]]} I would make Louise play the same thing over and over till she knew it. Went to see Miss Rose.

October 22. Sun. Mother went to Church with me in the evening. Brought home my books for Father has not mentioned about the pews but I'm sure they will never be

Mon. 23. A man came to take our apartments, and ordered tea with eggs &c. Mother requested him to pay a week in advance. He appeared quite willing, but when Father came in he wished him to settle for his tea then, so he walked off.

Tues. 24. Singing lesson. Miss Nunn gave me an Italian Song very pretty for the first.

Wed. 25. Went into Sims to invite them in tomorrow evening and staid to supper.

Thurs. 26. Came nearly all the way home with the Kemps early in the afternoon. Spent a very pleasant eve. Fred did not come Annie Smith and her Brother Willie came. Miss Goom called. The ~~Smiths~~ Sims were in also.

Fri. Went to have my hair done at Kennedy's house, rather late. Mother went to Sims to see if I was there. They were going off in a hurry to look for me when I returned. Miss Woodford and Miss George came.

Sat. 28. Edward Sims came to meet me in the Park. Went to have a singing lesson and from there went on to Kensington as I promised Emma. Did not get there till after 9. Emma had been to the exhibition to hear the French Band, A very grand day. Military Fete.

Sun. 29. Went to the Chapel in the Palace with Mr. Date in [[27] the morning. In the evening to Kensington church with Emma and Fred. He came and saw me into an Omnibus.

Oct. 30. Mon. Found Mrs. Anderson at our house when I got home. Did not find her much better. She is very unwell and remained all night. Miss Giere called.

Tues. 31. Mrs. Wallace came and made rather a surprising proposal to Mother respecting John and me. I called in. The boy took my Merino dress to be made. Had a tumble.

November 1. Wed. So foggy I did not like to go across the park. Miss Woodford and Miss Giere came in the evening.

Thurs. 2. Had a singing lesson but not a Music lesson as Orpheus was going to Waterfields.

Fri. Left Kemps at 2 and called on Mrs. Raggett. staid about an hour. went into Sims in the eve. Had some Music and a lobster supper. Ann's sister came and was ill.

Sat. 4. Went with Mrs. Sims and Mrs. Wallace to the Polytechnic, was to have met Mrs. Woodward, but did not see her there. Miss Glyn read Shakespeare's "Romeo and Juliet" very well indeed. the first readings I have heard. When I got home found Miss Woodford and her brother. They brought the carriage on purpose to take me back with them, but I would not go. She pressed it much because it is the last Sunday. they will have at Chelsea.

Sun. Went to St. Mary Magdalene's. Did not know it began so soon as 1/2 past 10 and over at 12. Went on to Fitzroy Sq. to call on Mrs. Rose. She was at Harrow. Went to Church in the evening, and intend going always.

[[28]]

Nov. 6. Mon. Had a singing lesson. Emma called just as I was starting and brought some cloth for a cloak. Ann's Mother came and took her sister away. Poor girl had been ill at one time for a week.

Wed. 8. Went from Carlton Villas in a Bus to Regents Street. Bought some Music and some trimming for my cloak. They are much more expensive than I thought, and will make my cloak come very dear.

Tues.7. Miss Giere came. I paid her. Mrs. Martin brought some Cloak patterns for me to choose and Miss Ladd came to try on my French Merino Dress.

Thurs. 9. Mrs. Kemp took all but Louise to the Lords Mayor's Show. When I came home, called in to Sim's. Edward had had a run thinking to meet me. Went to Miss

Nunn's. Had an English Ballard "I'll speak of thee" &c. When I came home read Guy Mannering.

Fri. 10. Found Miss Rose at our house when I returned. She stayed to tea. I was so pleased to see her, it reminds me of the many happy hours I have spent with them. I wish Mrs. Baldwin would write to me. Mrs. R. thinks I have improved with my singing.

Sat. 11. Did not feel inclined to have a singing lesson. Edward Sims came in and asked me to go in there to have a practice. Bought a front for my last years velvet bonnet and some Books at Ellis's, and then went in as I promised. Mrs. Martin sent home my cloak, Miss Ladd my dress, beginning my winter clothes.

Sun. 12. Went to St. Marks in the morning with Father. In the afternoon to Fitzroy Sq. to take tea with Miss Rose. Went to Trinity Church in the eve. Had such a long sermon, for the Young Man's Christian Association. went into Sims when I came back.

[[29]]

Mon. Nov. 13. Left Carlton Villas at 1/2 past 2 and went to Miss Rose to get her to go with me to buy a bonnet as she offered to lend me money. Went to Baker Street and ordered a brown one to be made. Had a singing lesson. Miss N. says I must lose

Tues. 14. Such a dark wet eveg. stepped into the puddles and was very glad indeed to get home. Wrote some letters. Miss Govier came and offered me a ticket for Exeter Hall for next Monday. which I was obliged to decline on account of the Rehearsal at Kemps.

Wed. Miss Wood came to have a German lesson just as we were starting to Jolliens. Persuaded her to go too. She took Mrs. Sims and myself in her chaise. Mr. S. and Edward met us. Saw Hannah Pringle there. Came home after first part. it was very fair but too noisy. Miss Woodford took me part at the way to Carlton Villas in the chaise, it being a very wet morning. Took a singing lesson in the evening. Began Kate O'Shane.

Fri. 17. Very wet morning and Mr. Sims walked all the way to Carlton Villas and had to return without an umbrella. I dare say he got very wet. Edward came in the evening, wanted me to go in there but I was too busy getting my dress ready to go to Kemps.

Sat. 18. Wrote in Mr. Kemp's Album. went into the Sims. Mr. Shepard Townsend and his Sister were there practising our new pieces which we are getting up for Christmas by the time John comes back. Nothing is thought about or talked about but the important event. I hear frequent hints but take no notice. I don't think they

will have it quite their own way. I shall be astonished if I leave England as soon as they do

[[30]]

Nov. 19. Sun. Met Emma at Rd, to go to Greenford. Johnny met us at Ealing. Found poor Uncle very ill indeed. Had been thro a severe operation of plugging his nose. He was too ill to get up. Went to call on the Smiths in the afternoon and returned to Halwell. Met Mr. Jason Gurney. Called at the Busters and then at the Sims to have a little singing.

Mon. 20. Took my dress with me and went round because would not meet any one and met every one I cared for. The Rehearsal did not go off so well as the last. Mr. Kemp was at York and did not return till 4 in the morning. Spent a very pleasant evening, but not quite as nice as the previous.

Tue. 21. Mr. Kemp very polite at breakfast. Had a very wet walk home. Left my dress. Took a bus in Edgeware Rd. and rode to the top of Albany St. Found a letter from Miss Rose awaiting me, went in to hear how he got on a Exeter. Still with Miss Govier last night he was much *[sentence incomplete]*

Wed. 22. Had a letter from Mrs. Baldwin. Miss Woodford and Miss Giere came. Poor Miss W.'s brother has met with a sad accident. He fell into a copper of boiling water and is very seriously injured, Poor Mrs. W. seems always in trouble.

Thur. 23. Went to Miss Nunn's. She wants a £ poor thing. I cannot let her have it myself, but hope Mother can lend it to me for a week. Mrs. Slater is going to Paris with Mrs. Rose for a friend of Miss Rose. It will be a very good thing for her.

Fri. 24. Went to ask Mrs. Sims to lend me "Angels ever bright and fair" to sing to Miss Yorker. They had a Magic Lantern but I did not stay. They had walked to Addison for the pieces that had not had a gentleman with them.

[[31]]

Nov. 25. Sat. Went to Miss Nunn's in the evening. Begun "Ever of Thee" I think it the prettiest song I have heard for a time. Miss Nunn is quite pleased with me and asked me if I would go there to a Musical party some night soon. I said I should have no objection.

Sun. 26. Went in the morn with Father to St. Marks. saw the Sim's there they waited for us and walked home with us. asked me to go for a walk. I would not when they came for me. Father said he hoped Ed. did not think anything of me. Went in the evening. Mr. Wilson was there they had letters for me.

Mon. 27. Ed met me at the Avenue Rd. Mr. Sims went with me all the way In the morning it was so cold, the 1st. winter day. It snowed. a little. I asked Ed whether

John was engaged that he was coming home to be married. So quickly he said he hoped he was. I don't know what difference it can make to him.

Tues, 28. Went to Miss Nunn for my singing lesson. Took my exercises to Louise to try. She likes them very much but it is too much trouble for her to learn them.

Wed. 29. Ed met me again. Miss Giere came. Had a note from Miss Woodford to say she would come but she did not. Have heard since she was not at all well. Miss G. stayed so long I was quite tired of her.

Thurs. 30. When I got home I was surprised to find Miss Rose Miss Anderson and a niece of hers. Mrs. A. is under Mesmeric treatment and really seems much better. It has almost made a convert of me.

[[32]]

December 1 Fri. left Carlton Villas at 1/2 past 3. Mrs. Wallace had first called. I went to ask her to come in again, but she declined. Took my singing lesson. Ann's sister is still very ill. Not expected to recover.

Sat. 2. Louise is so dreadfully tiresome with her Music, I am ashamed to sit and hear her take her lesson. I really will speak to her Papa, I cannot get her to practice as she ought to do. She is better in many things but dreadful in that. Something must be done. Mrs. Wallace and Mrs. Cammell with her baby, the 1st. time I had seen it. Mrs. W. said she must "*[text missing]*" and looked at me.

Sun. 3. Went to Greenford. Johnny came to meet me, found Uncle much better. Aunt and I went to Church. was so surprised to find a new servant. Aunt will miss Caroline very much. Mrs. and Mr. Gurney came over after tea. Returned by the 1/2 past 6. Walked from Rd. Called in at Sims.

Mon. 4. Ed Sims met me. I was not very cheerful. He was dreadfully attentive. Ish. Ed wanted to come and fetch me but I would not consent.

Tues. 5. After tea went to Mrs. Rose to fetch her to go with me to hear Miss Glyn. Thought she was going to read "Hamlet" but it was Romeo and Juliet again. I was rather disappointed. I sh. rather had heard something that I had not done before.

Wed. 6. Miss Giere and Miss Woodford paid Miss Giere 10-6. I had a new German book to read which I think I shall like very much.

Thurs. 7. Mrs. Rose called took tea and staid long enough to spoil my practice. but not stay all the evening. She expects [[33]] to go to Witney the beginning of next week.

Dec. 8. Fri. Had a Singing lesson. Left Carlton Villas at 1/2 past 2. Walked down to Regents St. pd. Addison called at the n Portland Bazaar to see Mrs. Martin's stall. Saw Mary. She looks very well for her. Visit to Lichfield. Went to Sims. Practised our

songs. Mr. S. had been to Hamilton Terrace expecting to meet me but as I came home so much before my time, missed me. I got very wet.

Sat. 9. Had a cold coming on. Went in the afternoon with Louise to buy some crackers to put under the chairs. I never saw such things before. She intends to have fun the next rehearsal.

Sun. 10. My cold very bad. Had breakfast in bed and did not go out till the evening and then Miss Govier came and went to St. Mary Magdalene's with me. did not go anywhere else.

Mon. 11. Je n'étais pas bien surprise de recevoir une lettre de E. S. dans la quelle el M. m offre son main et son fortune C'est bien redicule je n'étais pas long temps en lui dormant réponse Il est venu dans en soirée et avait l'ai bien misérable nous me demand y aller avec lui a un Concert Mercredi.

Tues. 12. On my way home called at Sims to say I could not go to the Concert. They made me stay to tea. Edward came all ready to go but did not do so when he found no one else was going. Sans doute il a recue ma lettre il est un homme ordinaire et est venue me conduisy a la maison.

Wed. 13. Miss Giere and Miss Woodford as usual the latter is going on Monday. to Miss Nunn's with me to hear her opinions about her voice. Had a good long German lesson. Miss G. is not particular about time.

[[34]]

Dec. 14. Thurs. Started after tea to call on Miss Wingate. She and the Children well and glad to see me. She is not at all pleased with Mr. Ellis does not suit her at all. Called at Sims Only saw Mrs. S. tho I heard both the others. They never come forward to speak which I think very odd. Staid there nearly and hour.

Fri. 15. Went to Miss Nunn's. She was too unwell to give me a lesson, so I would n't have one from Orpheus. Went on to Regent St. and bought a neck ribbon. When I got home began practising and who should walk in but E. S. to enquire how my cold was. He did not stay very long.

Sat. 16. Another rehearsal at Carlton Villas when all the performers are to be present. I don't think it so well as the 1st. Saw Miss Previte. Was not much taken with her. She is agreeable but that's all. Mrs. Pyne Galtons and Mr. Metcalfe were there too. They are not very aristocratic. The young men are passible. Young Messent the most gentlemanly of any but the Kemps think him conceited. I feel dreadfully nervous just when I am going to speak, but I hope I shall not be on the night. Mr. I Little saw me home. Presque.

Sun. 17. Emma's birthday. Went over there in the morning. Found Mr. Date very poorly. I thought to have seen Fred and Sidney but they were spending the day at

Hackney. Went to Kensington Church in the evening, and called on Mrs. Harrington in the but she had company and did not see me.

Mon. 18. Went to Miss Nunn in the evening. She was very poorly but managed to give me my lesson. Expected Miss Woodford to meet me there but she did not come [[35]] home. He called in the morning and went to the Election with Father. Went in there to tea. Mr. Wilson was there. John does not seem altered. Was very agreeable. He's a nice fellow. Ed. Sims was not well so did not make his appearance. Mr. Sims very cool I fancy.

Dec. 20. Wed. Miss Giere and Miss Woodford came. I told them I should not take a lesson next week.

Thurs. 21. John walked across the Park with me and had a job to get home again. Wanted to meet me. I told him "no". Went to Miss Nunn's in the evening to take a lesson.

Fri. 22. Went to the Poly with John and the Sims Very much entertained. Had the piano taken up in the 2nd. floor.

Sat. 23. My 23rd anniversary [*birthday*]. Louise gave me a little present. Went out to make some calls with her and her Brother. She introduced me as her Aunt. Mr. John and Mrs. Wallace and the 3 Sims came to tea. John gave me a piece of gold and Emma sent me Moore's "Irish Melodies". We spent a very pleasant evening. They stayed to supper and had some Music, of course. I told Louise I should take a week's Holiday.

Sun. 24. Father and I went to St. Mark's. John and the Sims were there too. I called on Annie Smith in the afternoon to see if she would come to our party on Thursday. She is engaged. John went to Church with me in the evening service at Mary Magdalene's at 1/2 past 10 came back and went to 1st Church of Christ.

Mon. 25. Went to the service at St. Mary Magdalene's in the morning. Willian Sully came to dinner. Sent and asked John to come in to speak to him. Father Mother and I went in there to tea. [[36]] Mr. Sims showed us the Magic Lantern and we spent a very merry evening.

Dec. 26. Tues. John call in the morning to know if I would go out with him. We went to Marlborough House, and the Geological Society. It is very nice to go with him, he is so clever and intelligent. Walked there and rode home. Did not go out again.

Dec. 27. Wed. Staid at home and wrote some letters. The Sims party is in the evening. The Townsends and Mr. Stevens there. John took me down to supper and sat next to me. Took me home and showed me every attention. I have promised to go out with him again tomorrow if it is fine.

Thurs. 28. John Came in about 1/2 past 10. I said I should not go out as I expected Aunt and was going to prepare something for the evening. He then said he had come home on purpose for me and made me an offer. I said I had no objection if he could get Father and Mother to consent. He went off to Father who was taken very much by surprise but consented. They came to dinner here and I went to the Langham Bazaar [with] Emma. Fred and his Brother and the Sims came in the evening. Strange day altogether but I am considered engaged.

Fri. 29. Very wretched in the morning. Went to the Crystal Palace with John and the Sims. I could not feel happy do what I would. He came home with me and Father and Mother formally gave their consent to our marriage.

Sat. 30. I had promised to go to Greenford and went by the 1/2 past 10 train. Walked all the way from H. as I missed Johnny. Aunt made such an attack upon me concerning this affair that I [[37]] determined to break it off. Uncle also opposed it very much. Had a game of Whist in the evening and will be here tomorrow when I must

Dec. 31. Sun. Went to Church with Uncle and Johnny. John Wallace came by the 10 o'clock train and came right away to Church. I was very cool all day. He went out with Uncle and when we were going home I told him I had been thinking of it and I had made up my mind not to have him. He was grieved and begged me to consider of it. I was so determined I said I would not and that I would not see him again. I felt very cool and very decided. When I got home and told Father and Mother they were astonished for Father had actually had some men to look at the Piano which was to have been sold. Capt. Anderson called and brought a note asking me to go there tonight or tomorrow. Father and Mother say he is a very nice fellow.

[note added later by?] On January 18, 1855. Mary Webster and John Wallace were married at Christ's Church, St Pancras, London, England, and sailed for America and California.

Diary of Mary Wallace, 12-14 July 1855. (WCP5567)

[[1]] *[note added later by?]* DIARY — MARY WEBSTER WALLACE — 1855 The following is from an old Diary. All of the leaves from January 1st to July 11th have been torn out. (She was then a bride of six months)

1855. Thursday, July 12. Went to Mrs. Kendals after tea John took me and went down town & in about 2 hours came & fetched me and sat a little time — — The day was very hot but evening pleasant.

1855. Friday, July 13. John at home all day finishing the plan & making the specifications of our ~~home~~ House. I went with Mrs. White and then to Cardinali's to look at his piano he wishes to sell. We left there about 9 and at 10 he was shot by the officers who were taking him in custody for illtreating his wife he is not expected to recover.

1855. Saturday, July 14. In the afternoon we went to sit with Mrs. Shaw Mrs. Brainard came in there with her baby Went up to the garden to gather some Tomatoes the first I had ever tasted. Then John & I went to see the Californian Lion the 1st time I had called on them in their new house.

Household expenses of Mary Wallace, January to October 1858. (WCP5568)

[[1]]

	January				
12	Miss Copeland	1.50	25	Washing	1.50
	Boots for Bertie	1.25		Meat	2.00
	Sundries to Pedlar			Letters &c	1.50
13	Coffee	1.00		Yeast	1.00
	Candles & Nutmeg grater	75		Washing &c sundries	2.50
	Beef	75	1 Mar	Water	1.75
	Steak	35		Chocolate	50
20	Mutton	50		Meat	25
	Steak	35		Crackers	25
	Ale	75	3	Berties likeness and postage	4.00
22	Teapot	1.25		Calico dress 2.00 Shoes for Bertie 75	2.75
	Crackers	50		Ale	75
	Onions	25		Potatoes \$1 Sugar \$2	3.00
				&c from Wheelers	
23	Meat 38 Sago 38	75	15	Washing	1.50

25	Meat	1.25		Meat for two weeks	2.50
	Stockings for Bertie	50		Fish 50 Crackers 25	1.25
				Rhu syrup 50	
	Apron for self	25	4	Milk	3.50
	Candle 50 Soap 50	1.00	18	Wheeler Bill	12.00
30	Sweet oil	62		Ann on a/ct	7.00
	Meat	38		Muslin	2.00
	Onions	25	20	Meat	
	Postage stamps	25		Soap Syrup Sugar &c	3.50
	Washing	4.50		White wool 50 / Green Borage 50	1.00
	Wrapper for Bertie	62	29	Meat	1.75
	Wages due 16 Jan to Ann	10.00		Bonnet	6.00
				Milk 3.50 Soap 50	4.00
	February			Drape Anns wages	15.00
1	Crackers	50		Drapes	7.00
	Syrup 75 Lamp oil 1/12	1.87		2 Weeks board	20.00
7	Lamps	1.50		Sundries	2.00
	Paid Phillips for dress &c	12.00		Plates dishes &c	2.50
	Mrs. Symenton	7.00		Laces	2.00
	Raisins &c	10.00		Washing	3.00
	Meat	75		Sundries	2.00
	Buttons & Cloth	1.12 1/2		Cover for lounge	5.00
	Shoes for self	1.75		Letters 50 — Soap 75	1.25
8	Milk	5.00		Gardener	20.00
	Can of Lobster	75		April (Probably)	
	Meat &c	1.50	15	Board, Mrs. Pownell	20.00
	Sundries	—		Mending Carriage	50

	Tick for bed, sheeting &c	3.50		Yeast rattle &c	50
	Candles	50		Lobster bread &c	1.25
	Sarsaparilla	1.50		Washing	3.00
	Mending glass window	75		Stockings &c	1.00
	Window Blind	1.75	20	Cuttings wood	1.25
12	Washing	1.50		Collar	1.50
	Meat	38		Sprinkler for hose	50
	Binding for Bed	1.00	21	Corn meal 25 hat for	2.50
	Chicken feed	5.00		baby 2.00	
	Velvet Ribbon	3.50			
	Sarsaparilla	1.50			
16	Anns wages on a/ct	8.00			
	Coffee	1.00			

H.A.W. 5-18-48

[[2]]

24	Milk J. Caroll came	1.75	Sept 24	Paid Johanna Carroll	15
	Ham	3.25		left unpaid	10
	Meat	75	Oct 24	Paid J.C. all due	35
	Cabbage	25		Paid with bill to Dec.	
	Mrs. Pownell for board	11.00		28th 1858.	
29	Shoes for Bertie & self	2.00			

H.A.W. 5-18-48

6 JULY 2024 BY CHRISTINE CHUA